

TEACHING STYLES OF ENGLISH TEACHERS IN DAET DISTRICT AND ITS EFFECT ON THE ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

The study aimed to determine the teaching styles of English teachers in a school district and its effects on the academic performance of the students. The study employed the descriptive-correlational research design. Data used in this study came from a survey of 37 English Teachers in Camarines Norte, Philippines. The study revealed that the respondents represent a wide range of backgrounds, primarily consisting of female teachers, with a notable number falling between 25 and 30 years old, predominantly holding a Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) degree, with some pursuing postgraduate studies, including both novice and seasoned teachers. Additionally, the English teachers collectively employ diverse teaching approaches. Favorable mean outcomes are evident across an extensive range of teaching styles like the Coach Style, Activity Style, Group Style, Blended Style, and Lecture Style, indicating a strong commitment to employing a versatile set of approaches in teaching English. Furthermore, the students demonstrate notably positive academic performance in English, with a considerable proportion attaining excellence in the "Outstanding" category. The cumulative general weighted average attests to commendable performance across various categories, reflecting a strong learning environment. It also revealed that there is no considerable correlation between the teaching styles implemented by English teachers and the academic performance of their students. The elevated p-value indicates that any observed correlation is likely coincidental. Therefore, the assertion "There is no significant relationship between the teaching styles used by English teachers and the level of academic performance of the students" holds true and meant that the academic performance of the students is not evidently linked to the teaching styles of the English teachers.

Keywords: *teaching styles, English teachers, academic performance*

INTRODUCTION

Teaching styles encompass the diverse methods and approaches educators use to impart knowledge, and they wield a profound influence on the quality of education (Gómez-Galán, 2020). As exemplified in the numerous studies, innovative teaching styles are imperative in the digital era, addressing the potent impact of information and communication technologies on students. Mismatches between students' learning styles and teachers' teaching styles can hinder academic performance, underscoring the importance of alignment (Chetty et al., 2019). Additionally, the assessment of teachers' competence through standards like the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST) illuminates areas for improvement and underscores the significance of continuous professional development in upholding teaching quality (Gepila, 2020; Jorilla & Bual, 2021). Overall, teaching styles play a pivotal role in shaping educational outcomes, emphasizing the need for adaptable, effective, and context-responsive approaches to ensure high-quality education.

Understanding teaching styles and their influence on student academic performance is a crucial aspect of educational research. Vermote et al. (2020) emphasized the significance of teachers' motivation and mind set in predicting motivating and demotivating teaching styles in higher education, shedding light on the complex interplay between educators' attitudes and instructional approaches. Similarly, Aelterman et al. (2019) proposed a circumplex approach to comprehensively analyze motivating and demotivating teaching styles, highlighting the need for a nuanced understanding of how teaching practices can affect both students and teachers. Furthermore, Chetty et al. (2019) found that teaching styles have a tangible impact on students' learning styles and academic outcomes, emphasizing the need to align teaching methods with students' preferences to enhance educational effectiveness.

Teaching styles and their impact on student academic performance are significant aspects of educational research. The effectiveness of teaching styles in various contexts is evident in recent studies. In the study by Invernizzi et al. (2019), the researchers investigated the effectiveness of an integrated approach, primarily based on integrating multi-teaching styles and active reflection (MTA), on fitness levels, motor competence, enjoyment, self-perception, physical activity, and children's perception of physical education (PE) in primary school children. The findings suggest that an integrated approach, led by specifically trained educators, positively influences children's physical literacy development, and promotes healthy lifestyles. Additionally, Odom's study (2019) focuses on the effect of professors' teaching styles and students' learning styles on achievement in a college classroom. This research highlighted the significance of identifying appropriate teaching styles to enhance student learning and satisfaction in the classroom.

Effective teaching plays a pivotal role in shaping students' educational experiences, as highlighted by the findings of recent studies. Inda-Caro et al. (2019) emphasized that teaching behavior, including a safe learning climate, efficient classroom management, and clarity of instruction, significantly impacts students' engagement and their perception of the learning environment. Sims and Fletcher-Wood (2021) underscore that effective teacher professional development, characterized by sustainability,

collaboration, subject-specificity, and practice-based approaches, directly contributes to effective teaching practices.

In Daet District, the English teachers use a mix of teaching styles to cater to the diverse needs of our students. Some teachers employ traditional methods, such as lectures and utilization of textbooks, to provide a strong foundation in grammar and vocabulary. Others emphasize interactive and communicative approaches, encouraging students to engage in discussions, group activities, and real-life language usage. Additionally, technology is increasingly integrated into the classroom, with teachers using multimedia resources and online tools to enhance language learning. Overall, the teaching styles in Daet district aim to create a balanced and dynamic English learning environment that suits different learning preferences and promotes effective language acquisition.

Despite the growing body of research on teaching styles and their influence on student academic performance, there is a noticeable gap in the literature concerning the specific context of English teachers in the Daet District. While existing studies have provided valuable insights into teaching styles and their effects, they often focus on broader educational settings or other subject areas. Therefore, there is a need for a localized investigation that examines into the unique teaching styles employed by English teachers in the Daet District and their direct impact on the academic performance of students within this specific educational environment.

The primary objective of this research is to address the research gap by conducting a comprehensive study on the teaching styles of English teachers in the Daet District and their direct influence on the academic performance of students. By examining the teaching practices and methods employed by English educators in this particular district, this aims to provide valuable insights into the dynamics of teaching and learning within this context. This study seeks to identify the various teaching styles utilized by English teachers and assess how these styles correlate with student academic achievement. Ultimately, this research was conducted to contribute valuable knowledge that can inform educational practices, teacher training, and curriculum development in the Daet District, ultimately enhancing the quality of English language education and student outcomes.

This study anchored on the Basic Education Development Plan (BEDP) 2030 serves as a strategic roadmap for the Department of Education to improve the delivery and quality of basic education and the experience of learners in the basic education learning environment. This study will help teachers to apply the most appropriate and preferred teaching style in executing the lesson. With that, it will improve the quality of education and academic performance of the students. As the Department of Education (DepEd) designed a new curriculum for the students, they also conducted training for the teachers using the teachers' professional development program for them to adjust their approach to the new curriculum. Aside from high demand of knowledge they want to implement to the students on the curriculum, forcing the teachers stick to the traditional approach, the main problem is not all teachers were reached by this program, not only by trainings but also some teachers are not flexible to a modernized approach in teaching.

As per DepEd order 42, s. 2016 discusses the instructional, methods and strategies of secondary school teachers. An instructional strategy is what a teacher uses inside the classroom to achieve the objectives of a lesson. A teacher can use a strategy or a combination of strategies to do this. These are the different instructional strategies used by the teacher these are Direct instruction, Indirect instruction, Interactive instruction, and experiential instruction.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 Age;
 - 1.2 Sex;
 - 1.3 educational attainment;
 - 1.4 teaching position and;
 - 1.5 length of service?
2. What are the teaching styles of the respondents in teaching English along the following style clusters:
 - 2.1 coach style;
 - 2.2 activity style;
 - 2.3 group style;
 - 2.4 blended style; and
 - 2.5 lecture style?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the teaching styles used by the respondents in teaching English and their profile?
4. What is the level of academic performance of students in English in terms of general weighted average?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the teaching styles of English teachers and the level of academic performance of the students?
6. Based on the results of the study, what learning and development plan may be formulated to improve the teaching styles of the English teachers?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

In this study, the descriptive-correlational method was utilized. The descriptive method served to provide an accurate and systematic description of the characteristics of the individuals, groups, or population under study. Specifically, in this research, the descriptive method was applied to discuss the focal concepts and variables of the study, including the profile of the respondents, the teaching styles employed by the respondents in teaching English, the level of academic performance of students in English, and the learning and development plan aimed at improving the teaching styles of the English teachers. Jim Frost (2022) defined descriptive statistics as numbers that summarize data, such as the mean, standard deviation, percentages, rates, counts, and range. Descriptive

statistics were employed to simply describe the data without generalizing beyond the data.

On the other hand, the correlational method was employed to determine and establish the relationship between two or more major variables in the study. In this research, the correlational method was specifically applied to determine the significant relationship between the teaching styles used by the respondents in teaching English and their demographic profile. Additionally, it aimed to identify the significant relationship between the teaching styles employed by the English teachers and the academic performance of the students in English.

Population, Sample Size and Sampling Technique

This study involved two distinct groups of respondents. The first group covered thirty-seven English teachers selected from five public secondary education schools within Daet District, Camarines Norte. In contrast, the second group of participants consisted of Junior High school students, at least one section that was taught by the English teachers chosen for this research. These two sets of respondents were drawn from the overall population of English teachers and Junior High School students in Daet District, Camarines Norte secondary education schools.

To ensure a representative sample, the selection of participants for this study utilized a total enumeration sampling. This total enumeration sampling method involved selecting one section of students per teacher intentionally. To allow for the inclusion of a heterogeneous mix of students, considering their unique characteristics and potential variations in academic performance.

Description of the Respondents

The sources of data for this study, namely the English teachers and Junior High School students, were selected using total enumeration approach. The teacher-respondents were chosen based on major criteria such as teaching qualifications and experiences in teaching the English subject. Meanwhile, the student-respondents were purposively selected based on criteria, including being currently taught by the respondents in the English subject during the current school year.

Research Instruments

In this study, a research instrument adapted and modified from Grasha (1994) was employed in accordance with the Statement of the Problem. The primary data collection tool was a survey questionnaire designed specifically for this research, aiming to align with the study's primary objectives. The survey questionnaire consisted of four main sections. The first section gathered pertinent demographic information about the teacher-respondents, including age, sex, educational attainment, teaching position, and length of service. Meanwhile, the second section focused on acquiring data related to the specific teaching styles employed by English teachers, categorized into the following style clusters: coach style, activity style, group style, blended style, and lecture style. The third

section gathered the general average of the learners by providing the numbers of students based on the descriptions given. The fourth section was the general average of the learners. The answers of respondents were measure using Rating Scale or Likert Scale. The respondents' answers were assessed using either a Rating Scale or a Likert Scale. The rating scale descriptors included "Strongly Agree" with a numerical value of 5, "Agree" with a numerical value of 4, "Neutral" with a numerical value of 3, "Disagree" with a numerical value of 2, and "Strongly Disagree" with a numerical value of 1. The teacher's response to the questionnaire was determined by the levels of agreement.

The collection of students' General Weighted Average (GWA) data involved accessing official academic records maintained by the selected schools in Camarines Norte. These records contained the GWA information necessary for the study's analysis. The adaptation and modification of the research instrument from Grasha (1994) were meticulously conducted to ensure its alignment with the study's specific objectives as outlined in the Statement of the Problem (SOP). This research instrument served as a valuable tool for gathering essential data pertaining to the teaching styles of English teachers and their potential impact on the academic performance of Junior High School students in the designated schools in Camarines Norte.

Data Gathering Procedures

Prior to the full implementation of the research, the study commenced with a thorough consideration of ethical principles. Various key aspects of ethical considerations were addressed before initiating the research, including the distribution of formal letters of request to the principals, district, and division research committees of the selected schools, seeking permission for the study and data gathering.

To ensure the reliability and validity of the survey questions, content validity was assured through the scrutiny of the questionnaire by five master teachers from schools outside of the locale of the study, ensuring that the instrument effectively captured the relevant dimensions of teaching styles. Considering the comments and suggestions of five master teachers, that there was no suggested revision of the content of the questionnaire. However, there were some words edited by the validator, but the content was the same.

To ensure the effectiveness and reliability of the data collection process, a dry run was also conducted. This dry run involved a preliminary test of the data collection procedures with twenty English teachers who were not part of original group of respondents. A sample of 20 respondents to identify and address any potential issues or challenges before full-scale implementation. The Cronbach's alpha was employed to assess the internal consistency of the items, ensuring that they consistently measure the intended constructs. Based on the results an alpha score exceeding 0.885 which indicates the questionnaire can be considered as good. The value of Cronbach Alpha is within the range of 0.60 to 0.80, it means that the value of Cronbach Alpha is moderate and acceptable. This iterative approach helped refine the data gathering methods and enhance the overall quality of the research.

Furthermore, the teacher-respondents underwent a short orientation to formally impart to them their roles and involvement in the study. Ethical letters of request were also dispatched to the teacher-respondents as a formal request for their participation, ensuring that they received assurances regarding the protection of their identities as respondents and informants, aligning with the principles outlined in the Data Privacy Act.

When all the ethical considerations were adequately addressed and complied with, the researcher proceeded with the implementation of the primary data collection methods and procedures. These data collection processes were meticulously designed to align with the core objectives of the study. For the first research problem concerning the profile of the respondents, data were gathered by administering survey-questionnaires to the English teacher-respondents.

Regarding the second research problem, which sought to explore the teaching styles employed by the respondents in teaching English, the researcher administered survey-questionnaires to the teacher-respondents. This helped identify the specific teaching styles utilized by the teachers, such as coach, activity, blended, group, and lecture types of teaching styles.

Additionally, for the fourth research problem, which centered on assessing the level of academic performance of students in English, data were collected from the teacher-respondents. They provided information on the students' average ratings across various performance indicators in English, employing a structured 5-point Likert scale to quantify these ratings. Furthermore, to complement this data collection, documentary analysis was utilized as a tool for determining students' General Weighted Average (GWA). Access to official academic records maintained by the selected schools in Camarines Norte facilitated the retrieval of this vital GWA data, ensuring a comprehensive evaluation of students' academic performance in English. This combined approach provided a strong foundation for the analysis of the research problem at hand.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The relevant data and information in this study were subjected to descriptive statistics for treatment, interpretation, and data analysis. Thus, for Problem 1 on the profile of the respondents, the data were statistically treated using the percentage method. Meanwhile, for Problem 2 on the teaching styles used by the respondents in teaching English, the researcher used frequency count and weighted mean for data treatment.

On the other hand, for Problem 3 on the significant relationship between the teaching styles used by the respondents in teaching English and their profile, Somer's Delta Correlation Coefficient and Contingency Coefficient were applied to establish the correlation between the two major variables and treat the data. In Problem 4 on the level of academic performance of students in English, the researcher also resorted to the use of the percentage method for statistical data treatment. Finally, for Problem 5 on the significant relationship between the teaching styles used by the English teachers and the

level of academic performance of the students, the researcher also utilized the Pearson Product Moment Correlation for data treatment and analysis.

RESULTS

Analysis and Interpretation of Data

The findings of this study answered the following: 1) Profile of the respondents; 2) their teaching styles in English along the different clusters; 3) the significant relationship between the teaching styles used by English teachers and their demographic profile; 4) the level of academic performance of students in English; 5) the significant relationship between the teaching styles of English teachers and the level of academic performance of the students; 6) the learning and development plan may be formulated to improve teaching styles of English teachers.

Profile of the Respondents

This part presents the profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, educational attainment, teaching position and number of years in teaching. These profiles are described in terms of their frequency in the second column and percentage in the third column.

Table 1. Profile of Respondents

Age	Frequency	Percentage (%)
25-30	8	21.6
31-35	6	16.2
36-40	5	13.5
41-45	5	13.5
46-50	5	13.5
51-55	3	8.1
56-60 and above	5	13.5
Total	37	100.00
Sex		
Male	5	13.5
Female	32	86.5
Total	37	100.00
Education		
BSED	18	48.6
With Units in Master	22	59.5
Master's Degree	4	10.8
Doctorate Degree	2	5.4
Total	37	100.00
Teaching Position		
Teacher I	14	37.8
Teacher II	2	5.4

Teacher III	12	32.4
Master Teacher I	7	18.9
Master Teacher II	1	2.7
Total	37	100.00
Number of Years in Teaching		
1-5	4	10.8
6-10	13	35.1
11-15	8	21.6
Above 15 years	11	29.7
Total	37	100.00

This table shows the age of respondents in different categories. The data revealed that age 25-30 has the highest frequency of 8 and the age 51-55 has the lowest frequency of 3. In terms of sex, the data shows that female has the higher frequency of 32 (86.5 %) than male with frequency of 5 (13.5 %). The data also shows the educational attainment of the respondents, the teachers with master's degree units have the highest frequency of 22 and the teachers with doctorate degree have the lowest frequency of 2. Regarding the educational background, more than half of the respondents have units in masters (59.5%) and only (5.4%) are doctorate degree holders. As for teaching position, teacher I (37.8%) being the highest, followed by Teacher III (32.4%), Master teacher I (18.9%), Teacher II (5.4%) and Master teacher II (2.7%) and Master teacher II are the lowest. When it comes to professional tenure, (35.1%) of English teachers are teaching for 6–10 years, whereas (21.6%) English teachers teaching for 11–15 years, and (29.7%) of English teachers were teaching for more than 15 years. The different ranges of years of service among the respondents give the group a wide range of views, showed that there are both experienced teachers and those who were just starting out in their careers. This profile analysis gives us a more complete picture of the respondents, who have a range of levels of experience, educational backgrounds, and places in the educational hierarchy.

Based on the results, the data revealed a wide range of ages among respondents, ranging from 25 to 60 years old. The age range of 25-30 years old is the most common among respondents. This indicates a significant prevalence of younger teachers in field of English teaching, maybe reflecting recent entrants or those in the early years in the profession. The diversity in age representation shows a wide spectrum of teaching approaches among the English teachers which can significantly influence their teaching styles. Particularly, most of the respondents are female teachers than male teachers.

In terms of educational attainment, more teachers holding bachelor's degree with master's degree units have the highest frequency. This indicates that most of the respondents are still improving their skills and knowledge by obtaining units in master's degree courses. This showed that English teachers in Daet South district still want to attain the degree so that they can use in their teaching profession. In teaching position, the data showed that Teacher I have the highest frequency of 14. This indicates that some of the respondents are holding the lowest teaching position. Lastly, in terms of the years of teaching of the respondents, majority of English teachers in Daet District served for six

to ten years in the department of education. It showed that those in the early stages of their professional journey. This could possibly mean that respondents served for almost ten years are fully equipped as a facilitator in the class.

The result of the study is supported by the study of Francisco (2020) investigated the effects of teachers' personal and professional demographic characteristics on students' academic performance in English. This study was related to the present study on how profile of the respondents increased the student engagement, improve learning outcomes and development of lifelong learning.

Teaching Styles in English Instruction

This part presents the Coach teaching styles of English teachers in English instruction.

Coach Style. Table 2 presented the five indicators of Coach teaching style, the weighted mean and interpretation. Based on the results, the indicators "I encourage students to learn from each other, ask questions, and actively participate in discussions to enhance their language skills" and "I encourage students to set their language learning goals, take ownership of their progress, and make choices regarding their learning paths" were the highest weighted mean of 4.7 and the indicator "I believe that students construct their understanding of English through active engagement and reflection. I facilitate opportunities for students to explore and apply language concepts in real-life situations, encouraging them to build their knowledge" got the lowest weighted mean of 4.5 with the overall weighted mean of 4.67 and with the same interpretation of Strongly Agree.

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1.I encourage students to learn from each other, ask questions, and actively participate in discussions to enhance their language skills.	4.7	Strongly Agree
2.I believe that students construct their understanding of English through active engagement and reflection. I facilitate opportunities for students to explore and apply language concepts in real-life situations, encouraging them to build their knowledge.	4.5	Strongly Agree
3.I encourage students to set their language learning goals, take ownership of their progress, and make choices regarding their learning paths.	4.5	Strongly Agree
4.I create a positive and supportive learning environment where students' unique needs and preferences are considered to foster their language development.	4.7	Strongly Agree
Overall Weighted Mean	4.6	Strongly Agree

Rating Scale:

4.21-5.00	-	Strongly Agree (SA)
3.41-4.20	-	Agree (A)
2.61-3.40	-	Neutral (NA)

1.81-2.60	-	<i>Disagree</i>
1.00-1.80	-	<i>Strongly Disagree</i>

The data revealed that the top coach style of teaching which were the indicator “I encourage students to learn from each other, ask questions, and actively participate in discussion to enhance their language skills” and indicator “I create a positive and supportive learning environment where students’ unique needs and preferences are considered to foster their language development” emphasize the facilitation of student-centered learning through active participation and collaboration. This aligns closely with constructivist theories of learning which argues that knowledge is actively constructed through social interaction. Furthermore, this meant that English teachers adopted teaching styles that promote active language learning and an environment conducive to language proficiency development.

The result is consistent with the study of Qureshi et al.'s (2021) investigation delved into factors influencing students' learning performance. The study specifically examined the impact of social factors on collaborative learning and engagement, emphasizing their consequential effect on students' overall learning outcomes. The findings underscore the positive influence of social elements, such as interactions with peers and teachers, on fostering active collaborative learning and enhancing student involvement. This resonates with the collaborative and engaging aspects highlighted in the Coach teaching style observed in the current analysis.

On contrary, the indicators “I believe that students construct their understanding of English through active engagement and reflection. I facilitate opportunities for students to explore and apply language concepts in real-life situations, encouraging them to build their knowledge” and “I encourage students to set their language learning goals, take ownership of their progress, and make choices regarding their learning paths” got the lowest weighted mean among the coach style indicators. The findings may reflect the rooted beliefs among English teachers to assume a directive role in imparting knowledge. Teachers may need professional development opportunities to effectively facilitate student engagement, reflection and enhance student’s language learning experiences.

This finding is supported by the study of Barkley & Major (2020) proposed that student engagement is the product of motivation (the driving forces of an individual’s behavior) and **active learning** (what students do to build their skills). It is important to understand that the mix of motivation and active learning is unique to everyone, and engagement is not stable over time or for an individual person.

This part presents the Activity teaching styles of English teachers in English instruction.

Activity Teaching Style Table 3 showed the five indicators of activity teaching style, the mean and its interpretation. Based on the results, the highest mean was the indicator “I encourage students to work collaboratively on tasks and projects. This promotes peer interaction, teamwork, and the development of interpersonal skills in English instruction” with the weighted mean of 4.8 and lowest mean was the indicator “I implement active learning theory by emphasizing that students learn best when they are actively engaged.

I design lessons to involve student participation through discussions, group work, and interactive exercises conducted in English” with the weighted mean of 4.5. The overall weighted mean is 4.67 with the interpretation of strongly agree.

Indicator	Mean	Interpretation
1. I provide hands-on, interactive experiences in English classes. Students engage in practical activities, games, and simulations that encourage them to apply language skills in real contexts.	4.7	Strongly Agree
2. I implement active learning theory by emphasizing that students learn best when they are actively engaged. I design lessons to involve student participation through discussions, group work, and interactive exercises conducted in English.	4.5	Strongly Agree
3. I incorporate various types of activities, catering to visual, auditory, kinesthetic, and other learning styles to ensure inclusivity.	4.7	Strongly Agree
4. I encourage students to work collaboratively on tasks and projects. This promotes peer interaction, teamwork, and the development of interpersonal skills in English instruction.	4.8	Strongly Agree
Overall Weighted Mean	4.67	Strongly Agree

Rating Scale:

4.21-5.00	-	<i>Strongly Agree (SA)</i>
3.41-4.20	-	<i>Agree (A)</i>
2.61-3.40	-	<i>Neutral (NA)</i>
1.81-2.60	-	<i>Disagree</i>
1.00-1.80	-	<i>Strongly Disagree</i>

The activity style of language teaching emphasizes active participation and collaboration among the students in the learning process. Indicator “I encourage to work collaboratively on tasks and projects. This promotes peer interaction, teamwork, and the development of interpersonal skills in English instruction” got the highest mean among activity teaching styles which indicates that the English teachers provide the students with collaborative activities that allow the students to practice expressing their ideas, negotiating meaning, and receiving feedback from their peers. With collaborative tasks such as group discussions, debates, and problem-solving activities, their social and cognitive skills are developed, enhancing their motivation and engagement in language learning.

The respondents “strongly agreed” on the indicators of the activity style. This meant that the English teachers share value of student-centered strategies. They provide opportunities for students to engage in meaningful dialogue and facilitate the development of communication skills while building positive relationship with their students as mentor in the learning process. This finding conforms to the study of study of

Erten and Atlay (2019) the effects of task-based group activities on students' collaborative behaviors in EFL speaking classes. The findings revealed that the comparison and the effects of task-based and topic-based speaking activities on student interaction and collaboration in EFL speaking classes.

On the other hand, the indicator "I implement active learning theory by emphasizing that students learn best when they are actively engaged. I design lessons to involve student participation through discussions, group work, and interactive exercises conducted in English" got a lowest weighted mean for the activity style suggests potential challenges or barriers to its effective implementation among English teachers in Daet District Schools. English teachers may lack sufficient training and support in implementing active learning strategies effectively. Without adequate training, they may struggle to design and facilitate interactive lessons. Additionally, limited access to instructional materials and technology may restrict the variety and scope of interactive discussions that can be incorporated into lessons, limiting student engagement.

This finding is corroborated by the study of Patiño et al.'s (2023) investigated into open education initiatives and Saad's (2020) exploration of computational thinking skills strengthen the credibility and applicability of active, collaborative, and hands-on learning methodologies. The instructional practices of English educators, as reflected in the surveyed teaching styles, harmonize with these research findings, underscoring the imperative of nurturing dynamic, interactive, and collaborative language learning environments.

Overall, data revealed that the English teachers utilize the activity teaching style. This proved that teachers are dedicated to creating an interesting and interactive language learning space. Programs for professional development and training can help teachers use activity teaching style more successfully, resulting in better learning outcomes and experiences for their students. All things considered, the evidence shows how beneficial and successful the Activity teaching approach is at encouraging participatory, team-based, and hands-on learning in the context of teaching English.

This part presents the Group teaching styles of English teachers in English instruction.

Group Teaching Style Table 4 showed the five indicators of group teaching styles, the mean and its interpretation. Based on the results, the highest mean was the indicator "I create opportunities for students to collaborate, share ideas, and construct knowledge collectively in English classes" with weighted mean of 4.7 and lowest mean was the indicator "I encourage students to take on teaching roles within groups, helping each other learn English. This fosters leadership skills and reinforces their own understanding of language concepts" with weighted mean of 4.5. The overall weighted mean was 4.6 with the interpretation of strongly agree.

Indicator	Mean	Interpretation
1.I create opportunities for students to collaborate, share ideas, and construct knowledge collectively in English classes.	4.7	Strongly Agree
2. I apply Vygotsky's ZPD theory by scaffolding group activities and projects to match students' current language abilities. This ensures that they are challenged but still supported in their language development.	4.6	Strongly Agree
3.I believe that students benefit from working together to solve problems, complete projects, and develop their language skills through shared experiences in English.	4.6	Strongly Agree
4.I encourage students to take on teaching roles within groups, helping each other learn English. This fosters leadership skills and reinforces their own understanding of language concepts.	4.5	Strongly Agree
Overall Weighted Mean	4.6	Strongly Agree

Rating Scale:

4.21-5.00	-	<i>Strongly Agree (SA)</i>
3.41-4.20	-	<i>Agree (A)</i>
2.61-3.40	-	<i>Neutral (NA)</i>
1.81-2.60	-	<i>Disagree</i>
1.00-1.80	-	<i>Strongly Disagree</i>

Indicator “I create opportunities for students to collaborate, share ideas, and construct knowledge collectively in English classes” got the highest mean meant that English teachers recognized the value of collaborative activities in promoting communication skills among the students. They structure their lessons to create opportunities for students to work together and collectively construct knowledge. Students are given the chance to work collaboratively with peers from diverse backgrounds and learn from different perspectives. This finding conforms to the study of Chen and Yu's (2019) investigation corroborated the finding of this study as it delved into shifts in students' attitudes, participation, and learning within collaborative writing. The study highlighted how student attitudes shape patterns of interaction and language learning opportunities in collaborative writing. The findings revealed that changes in student attitudes influenced group interaction patterns, aligning with the nuanced analysis of each indicator in the Group teaching style. Factors like English-learning beliefs, the perceived value of peer assistance, and group dynamics emerged as influential in shaping students' attitudes toward collaborative writing. This alignment extends to the motivation for students to assume teaching roles within groups (mean score of 4.5) in the present analysis, emphasizing the cultivation of leadership skills and the reinforcement of language concept comprehension.

This implied that English teachers are dedicated to creating a space where students can work together and talk to each other. It means putting more emphasis on interactive learning, which let students work together with their classmates to share ideas and build knowledge as a group in language class. The overall mean of 4.6 consolidates these findings, depicting a strong and unwavering adherence to the Group teaching style. This approach is characterized by a dedication to collaborative learning, the practical application of Vygotsky's ZPD theory, and the motivation for students to embrace teaching roles within groups.

Nevertheless, the indicator "I encourage students to take on teaching roles within groups, helping each other learn English. This fosters leadership skills and reinforces their own understanding of language concepts" got the lowest mean, indicating that the English teachers occasionally empowered the students to take on active roles in their own learning. However, the low weighted mean suggests that there are factors that teacher refrain from regularly doing this style. One factor could be difficulties in managing group dynamics, especially in large, highly diverse classes. Another factor could be the poor peer teaching and leadership skills of the students in teaching English concepts among their peers. This is supported by the study of Rana and Rana (2022) in Nepal, the awareness of collaborative learning strategies among secondary English teachers was scrutinized. The results disclosed that collaborative language learning activities in classrooms were constrained, often overshadowed by traditional pedagogy. Effective collaborative learning strategies, such as group work, peer support, and dialogue, were pinpointed—correlating with the collaborative and interactive dimensions underscored in the overall mean of the Group teaching style (4.6). The study underscored that teachers' limited familiarity with collaborative learning acted as a hindrance to its widespread implementation, underscoring the significance of comprehensive training.

In English lessons, teachers should keep providing opportunities for collaborative learning by utilizing group projects, activities, and cooperative problem-solving exercises. By using instructional scaffolding to implement Vygotsky's ZPD theory, group activities can be made to be both properly difficult and beneficial for students' language development. Through peer teaching and collaboration, encouraging students to assume teaching roles within groups can foster leadership qualities and enhance their comprehension of linguistic ideas. The research, taken as a whole, highlights the benefits and efficacy of group teaching approaches in encouraging cooperative learning settings and assisting students' language development during English instruction.

Furthermore, Zhetpisbayeva and Shalbayeva's (2019) aligns with the results of this study. It explored the application of Vygotsky's "Zone of Proximal Development" theory in teaching foreign languages within inclusive education. The theory, which aligns with the practical application of Vygotsky's ZPD theory underscored in the overall mean of the Group teaching style (4.6), was discussed in terms of methods and scaffolding. This aligns seamlessly with the educators' commitment to scaffold group activities and projects to align with students' current language abilities.

Overall, data revealed that English utilized group teaching style. The overall weighted mean of 4.6 indicated that teachers believe that students working together

develop their language skills. The overall weighted mean meant that teachers in Daet District schools give opportunities for students to collaborate and shares ideas in English classes.

This part presents the Blended teaching styles of English teachers in English instruction.

Blended Teaching Style Table 5 showed the five indicators of blended teaching styles, the mean and its interpretation. Based on the results, the highest mean was the indicator “I incorporate digital resources, online platforms, and multimedia materials to enhance language instruction and provide opportunities for self-paced learning in English” with weighted mean of 4.6 and indicator “I implement elements of the flipped classroom model, which is rooted in constructivist theory. Students access online materials and resources before class, allowing our in-class time to focus on active learning, discussions, and practical applications of English concepts” got the lowest mean score with weighted mean of 4.0. The overall weighted mean was 4.32 with the interpretation of strongly agree.

Indicator	Mean	Interpretation
1. I incorporate digital resources, online platforms, and multimedia materials to enhance language instruction and provide opportunities for self-paced learning in English.	4.6	Strongly Agree
2. I encourage students to connect with online communities, access relevant content, and explore a wide range of digital tools to facilitate language learning in English.	4.2	Agree
3. I implement elements of the flipped classroom model, which is rooted in constructivist theory. Students access online materials and resources before class, allowing our in-class time to focus on active learning, discussions, and practical applications of English concepts.	4.0	Agree
4. I combine traditional in-class instruction with online components. This approach allows students to benefit from both face-to-face interactions and the flexibility of digital resources for language learning in English.	4.5	Strongly Agree
Overall Weighted Mean	4.32	Strongly Agree

Rating Scale:

4.21-5.00	-	<i>Strongly Agree (SA)</i>
3.41-4.20	-	<i>Agree (A)</i>
2.61-3.40	-	<i>Neutral (NA)</i>
1.81-2.60	-	<i>Disagree</i>
1.00-1.80	-	<i>Strongly Disagree</i>

The indicator “I incorporate digital resources, online platforms, and multimedia materials to enhance language instruction and provide opportunities for self-paced learning in English” got the highest weighted mean. This meant that with access to online platforms and multimedia materials, students can engage in language content even if they are at home, enabling asynchronous learning and self-directed exploration. Also, multimedia materials accessed online appeals to the visuals, kinesthetic, and auditory preferences of the students which results in deeper understanding of English concepts. Furthermore, the dedication to cultivating a versatile, technology-enhanced language learning environment, evident in the nuanced analysis of each indicator and the overall mean, finds corroboration in Rao's exploration of Blended Learning (2019). The concept of blended learning, as Rao describes it, aligns with the present study's emphasis on combining traditional in-class instruction with online components. Both studies underscore the benefits derived from integrating multiple learning delivery mediums, emphasizing that learning is a continuous process facilitated by a blend of traditional and digital resources.

The indicator “I implement elements of the flipped classroom model, which is rooted in constructivist theory. Students access online materials and resources before class, allowing our in-class time to focus on active learning, discussions, and practical applications of English concepts” got the lowest weighted mean of 4.0, the interpretation was Agree. This implied that teachers in Daet South Schools maybe have difficulties in accessing internet connections and some students considered as technology independence. This model also can increase preparation time for teachers and can present challenges to students. Possibly teachers are not yet ready for the application of the flipped classroom model because of lack of trainings. Also, students have not any exposure in this kind of set-up, they really need the guidance of their parents and teachers as well. The results aligned with the study of Alhujaylan's (2019) investigation into the effectiveness of Computer-Assisted Language Learning (CALL) in teaching English writing skills in Saudi Arabia acknowledges the role of technological integration for enhanced learning outcomes. This aligns with the technological adaptability implicit in the current analysis of the Blended teaching style, where digital resources are incorporated into language instruction.

Overall, the data revealed that English teachers utilized blended teaching style. This showed that combination of traditional in-class instruction and incorporating of multimedia resources creating a lively, tech-filled learning space that encourages students to learn at their own pace. The total mean score meant a strong and steady dedication to the blended teaching style. This way of teaching combines digital tools, online platforms, and multimedia materials in a way that does not feel difficult. This showed that English teachers in Daet district are still committed to creating a flexible, tech-enhanced language learning environment. The findings of the present analysis, reflected in the overall mean of 4.32, align seamlessly with the insights from studies on technology-enhanced language learning and teaching. The strong and unwavering commitment to the Blended teaching style, as characterized by the seamless integration of digital resources, online platforms, and multimedia materials, resonates with the overarching theme in the review conducted by Shadieff and Yang (2020). Their comprehensive examination of research articles highlighted the increasing prominence

of technology-enhanced language learning, emphasizing the diverse technologies employed and the continuous evolution of teaching methodologies.

This part presents the Lecture teaching styles of English teachers in English instruction.

Lecture Teaching Style Table 6 showed the five indicators of lecture teaching styles, the mean and its interpretation. Based on the results, there were 3 highest indicators with the same weighted mean of 4.8. These were indicators “I provide clear explanations and structured content delivery. I use lectures to present essential language concepts and reinforce learning through repetition and practice in English”, “I break down complex language concepts into manageable segments during lectures. This helps students process and understand English content step by step”, and “I aim to manage the cognitive load by presenting information effectively, using visuals, and minimizing extraneous distractions to enhance students’ comprehension”. The lowest mean score was the indicator “I adapt my teaching approach to match the proficiency levels of students, ensuring that explanations and content are appropriate and effective for their language learning in English” with weighted mean of 4.5. The overall weighted mean was 4.72 with the interpretation of strongly agree.

Indicator	Mean	Interpretation
1. I provide clear explanations and structured content delivery. I use lectures to present essential language concepts and reinforce learning through repetition and practice in English.	4.8	Strongly Agree
2. I break down complex language concepts into manageable segments during lectures. This helps students process and understand English content step by step.	4.8	Strongly Agree
3. I aim to manage the cognitive load by presenting information effectively, using visuals, and minimizing extraneous distractions to enhance students' comprehension.	4.8	Strongly Agree
4. I adapt my teaching approach to match the proficiency levels of students, ensuring that explanations and content are appropriate and effective for their language learning in English.	4.5	Strongly Agree
Overall Weighted Mean	4.72	Strongly Agree

Rating Scale:

4.21-5.00	-	<i>Strongly Agree (SA)</i>
3.41-4.20	-	<i>Agree (A)</i>
2.61-3.40	-	<i>Neutral (NA)</i>
1.81-2.60	-	<i>Disagree</i>

The data revealed that the indicators with the highest mean score were “I provide clear explanations and structured content delivery. I use lectures to present essential language concepts and reinforce learning through repetition and practice in English”, “I break down complex language concepts into manageable segments during lectures. This helps students process and understand English content step by step”, and “I aim to manage the cognitive load by presenting information effectively, using visuals, and minimizing extraneous distractions to enhance students’ comprehension”. This implied that teachers in Daet District Schools applied teacher-centered method by giving clear explanations, presenting information effectively and using visual presentation so that learners can easily understand the lesson. It showed that teachers are dedicated to creating a space where students can understand language ideas through well-organized and personalized lessons. This finding conforms the study by Rinekso and Muslim (2020), an exploration of synchronous online discussion for teaching English during the COVID-19 pandemic reveals a focus on online modes while aligning with the principles of effective communication and structured content delivery inherent in the Lecture teaching style. The positive student responses underscore the significance of well-organized and clear communication, elements integral to the Lecture teaching approach.

On the other hand, the lowest indicator “I adapt my teaching approach to match the proficiency levels of students, ensuring that explanations and content are appropriate and effective for their language learning in English” meant that possibly English teachers believe that a particular teaching approaches does not align with the needs and learning styles of students in English instructions. Also, teachers may not have enough trainings and professional development in a certain teaching approach to match the proficiency level of students. The results are consistent with the study of Tang's (2020) research delving into the challenges and importance of teaching English as a medium of instruction (EMI) in Thailand International College, while differing from traditional lecture-style teaching, emphasizes the importance of language improvement and subject matter learning. These aspects resonate with the commitment to clear explanations and adaptability to students' proficiency levels, as evident in the Lecture teaching style.

The Overall Mean of 4.6 revealed that there is broad agreement among teachers about the best lecture teaching styles for teaching English language skills. The teachers' great commitment to providing clear explanations, delivering structured information, and breaking down complicated language topics into manageable portion during lectures is evident from the consistently high mean ratings across all indicators, all of which were evaluated at 4.8. This suggests a shared commitment to supporting learning through gradual comprehension and strengthening important language concepts through practice and repetition. This finding conforms the study of Soleimani's (2020) delves into the intricate connection between English language teachers' epistemological beliefs and their predominant teaching styles. While not directly comparable to the overall mean, the findings suggest a profound influence of teachers' beliefs about the source of knowledge on their teaching styles. This alignment underscores the notion that educators' underlying

beliefs and values significantly contribute to their preferences for specific teaching approaches.

Additionally, the investigation by Arnas and Assiddiq (2021) focuses on the characteristics and teaching styles of effective English teachers. Although centered on effectiveness rather than collective agreement, the study emphasizes the diverse array of teaching styles employed by effective teachers, encompassing facilitator, personal model, delegator, impressive, and self-check styles. This diversity mirrors the collective commitment reflected in the Overall Mean to a variety of teaching styles.

Furthermore, Jiang and Zhang's study (2021) delves into the relationship between university teachers' teaching styles and students' agentic engagement in EFL learning in China. Despite emphasizing student engagement rather than teacher agreement, the study accentuates the impact of perceived autonomy support, social relatedness, and controlling teaching styles on students' agentic engagement. This alignment resonates with the Overall Mean's recognition of the paramount importance of employing a diverse range of pedagogical approaches.

Test for Significant Relationship between the Teaching Styles used by English Teachers and their Profile

Table 7 shows the profile of the respondents in the first column in terms of age, sex, educational attainment, teaching position and length of service and the relationship between the teaching styles used by the teachers on the following columns.

To test the significant relationship between the profile of the respondents and their teaching styles, Somer's Delta Correlation Coefficient and Contingency Coefficient were used. The statistical analysis conducted on the test for a significant relationship between the teaching styles used by teachers and their age profile revealed a negative correlation of $-.165$ for the coach style, but this was not statistically significant with a p-value of $.062$. Similarly, for the other teaching styles such as activity ($d = -.024$, $p\text{-value} = .731$), group ($d = -.081$, $p\text{-value} = .314$), blended ($d = -.037$, $p\text{-value} = .739$), and lecture ($d = -.042$, $p\text{-value} = .646$), there were no significant relationships found with age as reflected in Table 7.

Further, the profile on sex and coach teaching style indicated a positive correlation of $.109$, but this correlation was not statistically significant with a p-value of $.571$. The same lack of significance was observed for the other teaching styles in terms of activity ($C = .006$, $p\text{-value} = .973$), group ($C = .169$, $p\text{-value} = .303$), blended ($C = .148$, $p\text{-value} = .370$), and lecture ($C = .077$, $p\text{-value} = .556$) in relation to sex.

Table 7

Test for Significant Relationship between the Teaching Styles Use by the Teachers and their Profile

Profile	Teaching Style									
	Coach		Activity		Group		Blended		Lecture	
	Test Statistics	p-value								
Age	-.165	.062	-.024	.731	-.081	.314	-.037	.739	-.042	.646
Sex	.109	.571	.006	.973	.169	.303	.148	.370	.070	.676
Educational Attainment	.077	.556	.101	.449	.093	.480	-.029	.837	.077	.556
Position	-.088	.539	-.024	.845	-.106	.436	-.178	.202	.051	.709
Length in Service	-.115	.286	.044	.606	-.009	.926	-.009	.949	.009	.933

*Significant @ 0.05 level

The analysis also explored on the relationship between educational attainment, position, and length of service with the different teaching styles. However, just like age and sex, no statistically significant relationships were found for any of these variables across all teaching styles. This suggests that the profile of the respondents may not have a significant impact on the choice of teaching style used by teachers. Thus, accept the null hypothesis. The results also implied that educational attainment, length of service and teaching position of respondents were no connection with their teaching styles. Teachers who attained master's degree units and teachers who attained bachelor's degree used the same teaching styles. Also, the length of service and their teaching position showed that there was no significant impact on their teaching styles. This could possibly mean that teaching styles used by the respondents was not based on their profile but based on their teaching performance.

The findings revealed a negative correlation between the coach style and the age profile of English teachers meant that as the age of the English teachers increases their teaching to adopt the coach style decreases. Older English teachers are less likely to exhibit coaching styles compared to younger teachers. The concept of 'pedagogical translanguaging,' as elucidated by Cenoz and Gorter (2020), challenges the conventional monolingual bias prevalent in English language teaching. It underscores intentional instructional strategies that integrate multiple languages, aligning with the core findings of Teng and Zhang's (2020) study, which delves into the effects of a self-regulated learning (SRL) strategies-based writing intervention on students' proficiency in their second language (L2) writing. This underscores the critical significance of effective communication and mutual understanding, principles that resonate with the core tenets of pedagogical translanguaging.

Based on the study, the positive correlation between the profile on sex and the coach teaching style implies that female English teachers have the tendency to exhibit characteristics related to coach teaching styles than their male counterparts. The results are consisted in the study of Getie and Popescu's (2020) study on factors influencing students' attitudes toward learning English in Ethiopia complements these insights by

spotlighting the impact of social and educational contextual factors on students' attitudes. Together, these studies underscore the imperative for a flexible and inclusive language teaching approach that recognizes the diverse linguistic backgrounds and individual learning needs of students.

Level of Academic Performance of Students in English in terms of General Weighted Average

Table 8 presents the student's general weighted average across different performance areas, the level of academic performance, frequency, and its percentage.

Table 8
Level of Academic Performance of Students in English in terms of General Weighted Mean

General Weighted Mean	Level of Academic Performance	Frequency	Percentage (%)
75 and below	Did not Meet Expectation	17	1.40
76-79	Fairly Satisfactory	72	5.94
80-84	Satisfactory	173	14.26
85-89	Very Satisfactory	395	32.56
90-100	Outstanding	556	45.84
Total		1213	100.00

The table revealed the students general weighted average in English class and its level of academic performance. Particularly, a (45.84%) of students do exceptionally well in the "Outstanding" level. In addition, students got 85-89 general weighted mean of (32.56%) fall into the "Very Satisfactory" level. Also, (14.26%) of students do well enough to be put in the "Satisfactory" level. The categories "Fairly Satisfactory" (5.94%) and lastly "Did not meet expectations" level with the percentage of (1.40%). This implied that English proficiency of students can positively affect their academic performance. This also showed that students are proficient in grammar, reading and writing which highly connected to their academic performance and achievement.

The study aligns with the study of Badar et.al (2020) The Impact of Teaching Methods on Academic Performance of Secondary School Students in Nigeria. Based on the result obtained in the study, teaching method has a great effect on students' academic performance and the analysis shows that the discussion and demonstration teaching methods greatly improve the students' academic performance than the lecture method which was passive, and teacher centered.

The investigation conducted by Ahmetović, Bećirović, and Dubravac (2020) regarding motivation, anxiety, and English performance in students highlights the intricate relationship among these variables. This correlation is echoed in Passiatore et al.'s (2019) exploration of self-efficacy and anxiety in English learning, emphasizing the critical role

of emotional components in the language acquisition process. Both inquiries underscore the imperative for effective pedagogical strategies to augment student performance, resonating with the outcomes of Ahmed Kadhim.Mezaal et al.'s (2020) study on the advantages of a blended teaching approach for Iraqi EFL students learning English. The integration of contemporary methodologies, such as blended learning, emerges as beneficial for honing language skills. Additionally, Chien et al.'s (2020) examination of peer assessment within the context of spherical video-based virtual reality (SVVR) contributes to this discourse by accentuating the positive influence of interactive and immersive learning settings on English-speaking proficiency. Moreover, the investigation by Neng Aprilia Purmama et al. (2019) into students' motivation in learning English affirms the pivotal role of motivation in the language learning process. Collectively, these studies underscore the nuanced nature of language education, highlighting the importance of considering emotional, pedagogical, and technological facets to enhance students' language proficiency.

Test for Significant Relationship between the Teaching Styles of English Teachers and the Level of Academic Performance of the Students

Table 9 presented the teaching styles of English teachers and the level of academic performance of the students.

The test for significant relationships of the variables considered were tested using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation (r). The student's academic performance was analyzed in relation to the teaching style of the teacher respondents. The statistical analysis revealed the correlation coefficient (r) and p-value for each teaching style category. The teaching styles included Coach, Activity, Group, Blended, and Lecture. The academic performance categories were the following: Did not Meet Expectation (75 and below); Fairly Satisfactory (76-79); Satisfactory (80-84); Very Satisfactory (85-89); and Outstanding (90-100).

The results showed that there was no significant relationship between any of the teaching styles and the academic performance of the respondents. The p-values for all the teaching styles were greater than 0.05, indicating that the results were not statistically significant. The correlation coefficients were also very low, ranging from -0.189 to 0.163, further supporting the lack of significant relationship.

Table 9

Significant Relationship between Teaching Style and Academic Performance of Students

Teaching Style	Did not Meet Expectation (75 and Below)		Fairly Satisfactory (76-79)		Satisfactory (80-84)		Very Satisfactory (85-89)		Outstanding (90-100)	
	r	p-value	r	p-value	R	p-value	R	p-value	R	p-value
Coach	.030	.899	-.020	.933	-.073	.760	-.081	.734	-.034	.888
Activity	-.040	.868	-.002	.993	-.067	.779	-.132	.580	.118	.621
Group	-.046	.849	.016	.948	-.189	.424	-.077	.747	.028	.906

Blended	.134	.573	.163	.492	-.179	.450	-.041	.865	-.010	.968
Lecture	-.050	.834	-.086	.719	-.130	.584	-.048	.840	.075	.754

We reject the null hypothesis because our results are more significant than the usual level of 0.05. This implies that there is not a major link between the ways English teachers teach and how well their students do in school. Since the p-value is high, it seems likely that any link seen between teaching styles and student success is just a coincidence. Hence, "there is no significant relationship between the teaching styles used by English teachers and the level of academic performance of the students. Thus, the hypothesis will not be rejected. There is no significant relationship between the variables considered.

The lack of significant correlation between the academic performance of students and the teaching styles of the English teachers suggest that the teaching style used by teachers may not have a significant impact on the academic performance of the students. Teaching styles alone does not influence the student outcomes. Students' factors such as student motivation, engagement, prior knowledge assessment measure, learning environment and external influences may play a more important role in determining their academic success. Further research is needed to explore these factors and their relationship with academic performance.

The investigation conducted by Chetty et al. (2019) on learning styles, teaching styles, and academic performance aligns with other research emphasizing the pivotal role of effective pedagogical strategies. Specifically, their study underscores the impact of discrepancies between learning and teaching styles on students' academic achievements. This coherence extends to Gupta's (2019) discourse on principles and practices for teaching English language learners, highlighting the necessity for diverse approaches tailored to the diverse needs of students, including those identified as English Language Learners (ELLs). Taleb Eli's (2021) exploration of students' perspectives on innovative and interactive teaching methods contributes further, affirming the positive influence of such methods on students' learning experiences.

Moreover, the work of Ali Ibrahim and Wafaa El Zaatari (2019) delves into the teacher-student relationship and its effect on adolescents' sense of school belonging, emphasizing the significance of positive interactions for overall development. Lastly, the study by Yaseen Alzebaree and Idrees Zebari (2021) delves into the characteristics of effective EFL teachers from the viewpoint of Kurdish high school students, offering insights into the qualities valued by students in their language instructors. Collectively, these studies underscore the interconnected nature of teaching styles, innovative methods, teacher-student relationships, and students' academic performance, emphasizing the importance of adopting a holistic and student-centered approach in education.

Summary

This study was conducted to determine the teaching styles of English teachers in Daet District and its effects on the academic performance of the students. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions: 1) What is the profile of respondents in terms of; 1.1) Age; 1.2) Sex; 1.3) Educational Attainment; 1.4) Teaching position; 1.5) Length of service; 2) What are the teaching styles of the respondents in teaching English along; 2.1) Coach style; 2.2) Activity style; 2.3) Group style; 2.4) Blended style; and 2.5) Lecture style; 3) Is there a significant relationship between teaching styles used by the respondents in teaching English and their profile; 4) What is the level of academic performance of students in English in terms of general weighted average; 5) Is there a significant relationship between the teaching styles of English teachers and the level of academic performance of the students; 6) What learning and development plan may be formulated to improve the teaching styles of English teachers?

The study involved 2 distinct group of respondents. The first group were 37 teachers in Daet South District and the second group were their handled advisory class from academic year 2021-2022. Descriptive-correlational method was used in the gathering and treatment of data. Frequency count and weighted mean were utilized to measure the teaching styles of English teachers in Daet District. Somer's Delta Correlation Coefficient and Contingency coefficient were applied to establish the correlation between the two major variables and treat the data.

Findings

The findings of the study were summarized as follows:

Profile of Respondents

1. Out of 37 respondents, most of them are female teachers with 86.5% and 13.5% of male teachers. In age distribution, age 25-30 got the highest frequency with 21.6% and age 51-55 got the lowest frequency with 8.1%. In terms of educational attainment, 59.5% have completed units in master's degree programs, 10.8% having a master's degree and 5.4 % having a doctorate degree. Teacher I 37.8% got the highest teaching position among the respondents and Master teacher II got the lowest frequency with 2.7%. When it comes to professional tenure, 35.1% English teachers teaching for 6-10 years and 10.8% teaching for 1-5 years in service.
2. Teaching Style
 - 2.1 Indicator "I encourage students to learn from each other, ask questions, and actively participate in discussions to enhance their language skills", and indicator "I create positive and supportive learning environment where students' unique needs and preferences are considered to foster their language development" got the highest weighted mean of 4.7 in Coach teaching style. Indicators "I believe that students construct their understanding of English through active engagement and reflection. I facilitate opportunities for students to explore and apply language concepts in real life situations,

encouraging them to build their knowledge” and “ I encourage students to set their language learning goals, take ownership of their progress, and make choices regarding their learning paths”.

- 2.2 Indicator “I encourage students to work collaboratively on tasks and projects. This promotes peer interaction, teamwork, and the development of interpersonal skills in English instruction” got the highest weighted mean of 4.8 in Activity teaching style and indicator “I implement active learning theory by emphasizing that students learn best when they are actively engaged. I design lessons to involve student participation through discussions, group work, and interactive exercises conducted in English” got the lowest weighted mean of 4.5.
 - 2.3 Indicator “I create opportunities for students to collaborate, share ideas, and construct knowledge collectively in English classes” got the highest mean of 4.7 in the group teaching style, and indicator “I encourage students to take on teaching roles within groups, helping each other learn English. This fosters leadership skills and reinforces their own understanding of language concepts” got the lowest weighted mean of 4.5.
 - 2.4 Indicator “I incorporate digital resources, online platforms, and multimedia materials to enhance language instruction and provide opportunities for self-paced learning in English” got the highest weighted mean of 4.6 in blended teaching style and indicator “I implement elements of the flipped classroom model, which is rooted in constructivist theory. Students access online materials and resources before class, allowing our in-class time to focus on active learning, discussions, and practical applications of English concepts” got the lowest weighted mean 4.0.
 - 2.5 Indicator “I provide clear explanations and structured content delivery. I use lectures to present essential language concepts and reinforce learning through repetition and practice in English”, Indicator “I break down complex language concepts into manageable segments during lectures. This helps students process and understand English content step by step” and indicator “I aim to manage the cognitive load by presenting information effectively, using visuals, and minimizing extraneous distractions to enhance students’ comprehension” got the highest weighted mean of 4.8. Indicator “I adapt my teaching approach to match the proficiency levels of students, ensuring that explanations and content are appropriate and effective for their language learning in English” got the lowest weighted mean of 4.5.
3. Significant Relationship between Teaching Styles and Demographic Profile
The analysis reveals the test for a significant relationship between the teaching styles used by teachers and their age profile revealed a negative correlation of $-.165$ for the coach style, but this was not statistically significant with a p-value of $.062$. Similarly, for the other teaching styles such as activity ($d=-.024$, $p\text{-value}=.731$), group ($d=-.081$, $p\text{-value}=.314$), blended ($d= -.037$, $p\text{-value}= .739$), and lecture ($d= -.042$, $p\text{-value}= .646$).
 4. Level of Academic Performance
A notable 45.84% excel in the "Outstanding" level, and 32.56% fall within the "Very Satisfactory" level. Additionally, 14.26% perform well within the "Satisfactory" level.

Despite lower percentages, the "Fairly Satisfactory" 5.94% and "Did not meet expectations" 1.40% level.

5. Significant Relationship between Teaching Styles and Academic Performance
The results showed that there was no significant relationship between any of the teaching styles and the academic performance of the respondents. The p-values for all the teaching styles were greater than 0.05, indicating that the results were not statistically significant. The correlation coefficients were also very low, ranging from -0.189 to 0.163, further supporting the lack of significant relationship.
6. Based on the results on the study, a learning and development plan on the identified lesser effective teaching styles used by English teachers was proposed.

Conclusions

Based on the findings, the following conclusions were made:

1. The respondents come from a wide range of backgrounds, with most of them being female teachers. The age range is evenly spread out, with the highest percentage of teachers between the ages of 25 and 30. Teachers come from a wide range of educational backgrounds. Almost half have a Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) Degree and more than half have taken up master's degree studies. Even with all these differences, the teaching positions are mostly filled by Teacher I and Teacher III, who are a mix of newly hired and experienced teachers.
2. The Teachers acknowledge the applicability of the different teaching styles in teaching English. The results across a wide range of teaching styles, such as the Coach Style, the Activity Style, the Group Style, the Blended Style, and the Lecture Style, show a strong dedication to using a flexible array of teaching approaches when teaching English.
 - 2.1 In terms of coach style, teachers facilitate student centered learning through active participation and collaboration.
 - 2.2 In terms of activity style, teachers provided opportunities for students to engage in meaningful dialogue and facilitate the development of communication skills while building positive relationships with their students as mentors in the learning process.
 - 2.3 In terms of group style, English Teachers structured their lessons to create opportunities for students to work together and collectively construct knowledge. Students are given the chance to work collaboratively with peers from diverse backgrounds and learn from different perspectives. Also, English teachers recognize the value of collaborative activities in promoting communication skills among students.
 - 2.4 In terms of Blended style, the English teachers showed a strong commitment to using technology to improve English language learning. A dedication to create a lively, tech-filled learning space that encourages students to learn at their own pace with access to online platform and multimedia materials, students can engage in language content.

- 2.5 In terms of Lecture Style, the English teachers applied teacher-centered method by giving clear explanations, presenting information effectively and using visual presentation so that learners can easily understand the lesson.
3. There is no significant relationship between teaching styles and demographic profiles. The non-significant p-values associated with age, sex, educational attainment, teaching position, and length of service suggest that teacher's preferences in teaching styles are not evidently linked to their profile.
 4. Students exhibit remarkably a good academic performance in English, with a substantial percentage achieving excellence in the "Outstanding" category. The cumulative general weighted average attests to commendable performance across various categories. Despite some fluctuations, the overall academic performance is overwhelmingly positive, reflecting a strong learning environment.
 5. There is no significant relationship between the ways English teachers teach and how well their students do in school. The high p-value means that any correlation that is seen is probably just random. This means that the statement "There is no significant relationship between the teaching styles used by English teachers and the level of academic performance of the students".

Recommendations

Based on the summary of findings and conclusions, the following are the recommendations aimed for implementation:

1. In response to the diverse profile of teachers, schools may design adapted professional development initiatives tailored to the unique needs and experiences of teachers. These programs ought to prioritize the enhancement of teaching skills, the integration of innovative methods, and the targeted resolution of challenges specific to language instruction.
2. While teachers in the study showcase a strong commitment to diverse teaching styles, there exists an opportunity to further holistic styles.
 - 2.1 Schools may offer training for professional development of teachers to effectively facilitate student engagement, reflection and enhance student's language learning experiences.
 - 2.2 School may conduct orientation during Learning Action Cell (LAC) sessions for teachers to create educational materials and activities.
 - 2.3 Schools may offer trainings designed to provide opportunities for collaborative learning by utilizing group projects, activities, and problem-solving exercises.
 - 2.4 Teachers encourage the seamless integration of varied teaching styles, placing emphasis on a harmonious blend of traditional and modern methods to effectively address the diverse learning needs of students. Teachers' emphasis on Blended Style, schools may provide support and training in the seamless integration of educational technology. This initiative will support teachers' proficiency in leveraging digital resources effectively, thereby creating a more dynamic and engaging learning environment for students.
 - 2.5 Schools offer training programs that equip teachers with techniques and modern pedagogy strategies that help them to better connect with, manage, and teach their students.

3. Given teachers' unwavering dedication to collaborative learning environments, schools may create avenues for teachers to exchange best practices, collaborate on lesson plans, and participate in joint projects. This collaborative ethos can foster a sense of community among teachers, significantly enhancing the overall teaching and learning experience.
4. Schools may continuously monitor systems to evaluate the efficacy of teaching styles concerning academic performance. Regular feedback mechanisms will empower teachers to adapt their teaching styles based on student outcomes, ensuring that teaching styles remain dynamic and responsive to the evolving education. In enhancing academic performance in English, schools may actively prompt teachers to embrace more student-centered strategies. These may encompass personalized learning plans, differentiated instruction, and methodologies that cater to various learning styles, guaranteeing that each student receives the support they need.
5. Given the absence of significant correlations between teaching styles and demographic factors, there is a compelling imperative for further research to delve into additional influences on teaching choices. Examining teachers' beliefs, attitudes, and perceptions holds the potential to provide valuable insights into the intricate decision-making processes associated with language instruction.
6. Schools may emphasize the significance of pedagogical adaptability through the provision of regular training sessions. These sessions ought to concentrate on arming teachers with the skills necessary to adapt teaching styles based on student needs, learning outcomes, and emerging educational trends. This proactive approach enables educators to navigate the evolving landscape of language education with greater efficacy.

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